

Lipophilic compounds in *Pulmonaria rubra* and their *in vitro* activity

Aleksandar Shkondrov¹, Ivan Stambolov¹, Magdalena Kondeva-Burdina², Ilina Krasteva¹

¹ Department of Pharmacognosy, Faculty of Pharmacy, Medical University of Sofia, Sofia, Bulgaria

² Laboratory of Drug metabolism and Drug Toxicity, Department of Pharmacology, Pharmacotherapy and Toxicology, Faculty of Pharmacy, Medical University of Sofia, Sofia, Bulgaria

Corresponding author: Aleksandar Shkondrov (shkondrov@pharmfac.mu-sofia.bg)

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Abstract

Pulmonaria rubra Schott (Boraginaceae) is a scarcely investigated congener of the medicinal species *P. officinalis*. This study aimed to characterize the lipophilic constituents of the dichloromethane extract from *P. rubra* aerial parts (PR-DCM) and to evaluate its antioxidant and neuroprotective activity *in vitro*, as well as its effects on monoamine oxidase (MAO) and major cytochrome P450 (CYP) isoforms. GC–MS analysis after silylation enabled the identification of virtually the entire extract (99.99% of the total peak area), revealing a profile dominated by non-volatile lipids, including unsaturated and saturated fatty acids (notably linolenic and palmitic acids), long-chain aliphatic alcohols, phytol, and phytosterols such as β -sitosterol and campesterol, while steam-distillable volatiles were negligible. In isolated rat brain synaptosomes, mitochondria, and microsomes, PR-DCM (up to 200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) did not show intrinsic toxicity or pro-oxidant effects, but significantly counteracted 6-OHDA-, *t*-BuOOH-, and Fe^{2+} /ascorbic acid-induced decreases in reduced glutathione and increases in malondialdehyde. At a concentration of 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, PR-DCM did not significantly inhibit human recombinant MAO-A, MAO-B, CYP1A2, CYP2D6, or CYP3A4. Overall, PR-DCM emerges as a promising source of lipophilic antioxidants with neuroprotective potential and a favorable *in vitro* safety and interaction profile, warranting further isolation of active components and confirmation in neuronal and *in vivo* models.

Keywords

Antioxidant, GC–MS, lipophilic compounds, neuroprotective activity, *Pulmonaria rubra*

Introduction

Pulmonaria species (Boraginaceae), commonly known as lungworts, have a long history of use in European traditional medicine. They are used in cases of respiratory ailments and inflammatory conditions. Modern phytochemical and pharmacological studies have focused almost exclusively on *P. officinalis*, revealing various phenolic constituents and many biological activities, while other representatives of this genus remain only superficially characterized (Chauhan et al. 2022). *P. rubra* Schott is a closely related wild spe-

cies distributed in Central and Eastern Europe, including Bulgaria and Ukraine, where it is documented in regional floras but scarcely investigated for its chemical composition or bioactivity (Gostin 2009; Fedoronchuk 2024).

Pulmonaria species contain lipophilic compounds, clearly documented for seed lipids and fatty acids. Seeds of *P. obscura* contain substantial neutral lipids and triacylglycerides (TAGs), consisting of polyunsaturated fatty acids (γ -linolenic acid, α -linolenic acid, and 18:4 fatty acids) (Yunusova et al. 2018). These neutral lipids and TAGs are classic lipophilic constituents.

Most published chemistry, however, has concentrated on polar phenolics rather than systematically characterizing all lipophilic fractions. In *P. officinalis*, most detailed work has focused on polar phenolic acids and glycosides (rosmarinic, lithospermic, salvianolic acids, caffeic acid esters, flavonol glycosides) in hydroalcoholic extracts (Krzyżanowska-Kowalczyk et al. 2018; Chauhan et al. 2022). These are largely hydrophilic, but the review notes the presence of fatty acids among *Pulmonaria* phytochemicals, implying additional lipophilic constituents beyond seed oil (Chauhan et al. 2022).

Lipid-derived metabolites are increasingly recognized as important contributors to membrane structure, cellular signaling, and stress adaptation in plants and may also underlie antioxidant and neuroprotective properties *in vitro* and *in vivo* (Barbosa and Siniossoglou 2024; Zhang et al. 2025). Despite this, the lipophilic profile of *P. rubra* aerial parts has not yet been elucidated, and no data are available on the potential neuroprotective effects of its lipid fraction.

Oxidative stress and mitochondrial dysfunction are central mechanisms in the pathogenesis of neurodegenerative disorders such as Parkinson's disease, where dopamine oxidation and reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation contribute to dopaminergic neuron loss (Stokes et al. 2002). Subcellular *in vitro* models employing isolated rat brain synaptosomes, mitochondria, and microsomes exposed to toxic agents, including 6-hydroxydopamine (6-OHDA), *tert*-butyl hydroperoxide (*t*-BuOOH), and Fe²⁺/ascorbic acid, are well-established tools for screening plant-derived neuroprotective and antioxidant candidates by monitoring viability, glutathione (GSH) content, and lipid peroxidation markers such as malondialdehyde (MDA) (Kondeva-Burdina et al. 2019). Such models also permit early assessment of potential interactions with monoamine oxidase (MAO) and key drug-metabolizing cytochrome P450 isoforms.

The present study aims (i) to profile the lipophilic compounds in the dichloromethane extract of its aerial parts by GC–MS and (ii) to investigate the antioxidant and neuroprotective potential of this extract in models of oxidative damage, as well as its influence on MAO enzyme activity and major CYP450 isoforms.

Materials and methods

Plant material

The flowering overground parts of *Pulmonaria rubra* were collected in April 2024 from a locality in Vitosha Mt., near Sofia, Bulgaria. The plant was identified by one of the authors (I.S.), and a voucher specimen was deposited at the Herbarium of the Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (№ 179530) for future reference. They were separated into two—the first half was frozen immediately at –40 °C, and the second was dried in the shade at room temperature.

Distillation of volatiles

The fresh plant material (40 g) was chopped and distilled with water (1:5) in a Clevenger-type apparatus for 8 h. The distillation liquid was collected and extracted three times with diethyl ether and chloroform, successively, and the extracts obtained (DE) and (C) were concentrated under a gentle stream of nitrogen. Both were dissolved separately in chloroform (1:10000) and subjected to GC–MS analysis.

Lipophilic extract and derivatization

The air-dried overground part (40 g) was pulverized and exhaustively extracted with dichloromethane by percolation. The extracts were combined and dried *in vacuo*. The resulting viscous extract (1 g) was named PR-DCM and stored at room temperature. A solution of PR-DCM was made in *n*-hexane (10 mg/mL). Silylation was performed with SigmaSilA (Sigma-Aldrich, Germany), followed by heating for 4 h at 50 °C in an airtight vial. Subsequent to the reaction time, the sample was cooled, extracted with *n*-hexane, and injected into the GC–MS.

GC–MS analysis

GC–MS was performed with an Exactive™ Orbitrap™ GC–MS (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Germany) system operating at 70 eV, ion source temperature 230 °C, transfer capillary temperature 260 °C, with split injection (1 µL, 20:1 ratio) at 250 °C injector temperature. A capillary column with 5% phenyl residues/95% methyl polysiloxane (TraceGOLD TG-5SilMS GC Column 30 m × 0.25 mm × 0.25 µm, ThermoFisher) was used. The oven temperature program was as follows: initial at 60 °C for 5 min, increased to 300 °C (rate: 6 °C/min), maintained at 300 °C for 5 min. Helium was used as the carrier gas (flow rate: 1 mL/min). The EI ionization mode and full MS–SIM scan were used (resolution 600, AGC target 1e⁶, maximum IT 200 ms, and scan range of *m/z* 50–450). Data collection and peak processing (GENESIS algorithm) were performed with Xcalibur 4.2.28.14 (Thermo Scientific, Germany). A calibration mixture of *n*-alkanes (C8–C40 Alkanes Calibration Standard, Supelco, USA) was used. The retention indices and the relative percentage were calculated using the capabilities of the software. Each compound was identified by Wiley Registry 10, 10R, and NIST 2014. Data was interpreted through the software NIST MS Search v. 2.2.

In vitro pharmacological activity

Old (2.5 years) male Wistar rats with body weight 200–250 g were used. They were purchased from the National Breeding Centre, Sofia, Bulgaria, and housed in Plexiglas cages (three per cage, 12/12 light/dark cycle, 20 °C ± 2 °C, humidity 72% ± 4%) with free access to drinking water and standard pelleted rat food 53-3 (ISO 9001:2008). Seven days' acclimatization was allowed, and a veterinary physician monitored the animals regularly. The Vivarium of the Faculty

of Pharmacy (registration certificate № 0072/01.08.2007) was inspected by the Bulgarian Drug Agency (№ A-11-1081/03.11.2011). Permission to work with rats was issued by the Bulgarian Food Safety Agency (№ 347, valid to 27.03.2028). All performed procedures were approved by the Institutional Animal Care Committee (KENIMUS). The principles stated in the European Convention for the Protection of Vertebrate Animals Used for Experimental and Other Scientific Purposes (ETS 123) were strictly followed. Immediately after decapitation, brains were taken and stored on ice. Brain tissue homogenate was produced with the respective buffer (Kondeva-Burdina et al. 2019). Immediately after harvesting, the subcellular structures were incubated with the tested extract and/or the toxic agent in a 5% CO₂ + 95% O₂ atmosphere.

Rat brain synaptosomes were prepared from old rat brains by multiple subcellular fractionation using a Percoll gradient (Taupin et al. 1994) with small modifications (Kondeva-Burdina et al. 2014). The content of synaptosomal protein was determined using serum albumin as a standard (Lowry et al. 1951). The synaptosomes were incubated with PR-DCM (200 µg/mL) alone, with either 150 µM 6-OHDA or with a combination of 150 µM 6-OHDA and different concentrations of PR-DCM for 1 h. The MTT test was performed to determine synaptosomal vitality (Mungarro-Menchaca et al. 2002). The level of GSH was determined using Ellman's reagent (Robyt et al. 1971).

The brain mitochondria were prepared by multiple, differential fractionation using a Percoll gradient (Sims and Anderson 2008). They were incubated with PR-DCM (200 µg/mL) alone or with either 75 µM *t*-BuOOH (Karlsson et al. 2000) or with a combination of 75 µM *t*-BuOOH and different concentrations of PR-DCM for 1 h. MDA formed in each sample due to the oxidative stress was measured as described in Shirani et al. (2019). Assay of GSH was performed with DTNB (Shirani et al. 2019).

Rat brain microsomes were prepared as in Ravindranath and Anandatheerthavarada (1990). They were treated with PR-DCM (200 µg/mL) alone. FeSO₄/ascorbic acid (Fe²⁺/AA)-induced lipid peroxidation (LPO) was initiated as described in Mansuy et al. (1986). The microsomes were treated with Fe²⁺/AA and different concentrations of PR-DCM for 1 h. The quantity of the lipid peroxidation product MDA was assessed (Deby and Goutier 1990).

Monoamine oxidase activity assay of both recombinant human MAOA (*h*MAOA) and MAOB (*h*MAOB) was performed using a fluorimetric method with small modifications (Held and Buehrer 2003; Dezsi and Vecsei 2017; Kasabova-Angelova et al. 2020). Pure *h*MAOA or *h*MAOB working solution in reaction buffer was used as a control. The enzymes were incubated with either PR-DCM (1 µg/mL), chlorgyline, or selegiline (1 µM) for 2 h.

A fluorimetric method for determining the activity of some isoforms of human recombinant cytochrome P450 with the following inhibitor screening kits (ISK, Abcam, Cambridge, UK) was used: CYP1A2 ISK (substrate 3-cyano-7-hydroxycoumarin, inhibitor α -naph-

toflavone); CYP3A4 ISK (substrate resofurin, inhibitor ketoconazole); and CYP2D6 ISK (substrate 3-[2-(N,N-diethyl-N-methylammonium)ethyl]-7-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin, inhibitor quinidine). The PR-DCM (1 µM, DMSO solution) was incubated with the isoforms for 2 h (Angelov et al. 2022).

The statistical analysis of the results was performed using the statistical program "MedCalc" v. 18 (MedCalc Software Ltd., Ostend, Belgium). Each experiment was performed in triplicate, and the values are represented as the mean of three ($n = 3$). A Mann–Whitney non-parametric test was used to examine the statistical significance of the results. When $p < 0.05$, $p < 0.01$, or $p < 0.001$, the differences between groups were accepted as statistically significant.

Results and discussion

There was no essential oil present in the plant material. The diethyl ether (DE) and chloroform (C) extracts, obtained from the Clevenger distillation water, gave no peaks in the chromatograms. This shows that steam-distillable volatile components are negligible in this species, at least under the examined conditions. This sets *P. rubra* apart from many traditional medicinal plants where pharmacological properties are often attributed to volatile terpenoids and indicates that any potential bioactivity of PR-DCM is more likely related to the lipid fraction.

Identification of the phytochemicals in the lipophilic extract of the overground parts of *P. rubra* (PR-DCM) was performed using the retention index and comparison to records in WR10, WR10R, and NIST 2014. The relative percentage was used to quantify the compounds in PR-DCM. The GC–MS analysis after silylation produced a chromatogram with clear, well-resolved peaks (Fig. 1) and allowed identification of virtually the entire extract (99.99% of the total peak area).

It contained mainly aliphatic non-volatile compounds, which were identified by their trimethylsilyl (TMS) derivatives (Table 1).

The main ingredients were from the group of fatty acids—linolenic acid (19%), palmitic acid (13%), and a corresponding ester of linoleic acid—1-linoleoyl glycerol (9%). Notably, these fatty acids are incorporated into the triacylglyceride composition of the overground parts, consistent with their roles in energy storage and membrane structure (Barbosa and Siniossoglou 2024). The detection of a methyl ester of 2-hydroxymyristic acid at around 11% additionally points to the presence of modified fatty acids that may have specific structural or signaling roles (Fu et al. 2025).

Beyond simple fatty acids, the high proportion (15%) of (*E*)-phytol, the main diterpene alcohol associated with chlorophyll (Gutbrod et al. 2019), underscores a strong contribution of chloroplast-derived lipids to the extract. In other plant systems, phytol functions as a precursor of tocopherols and other bioactive molecules, so its abundance may be relevant for antioxidant potential (Hoseini et al. 2021).

Figure 1. GC-MS chromatogram (TIC) of PR-DCM after silylation.

Table 1. Identified compounds.

Peak №	t_R , min	Identified compounds	%	Prob. %	RI	Formula	Mm
1.	14.28	1,3-bis(trimethylsilyloxy)propan-2-yloxy-trimethyl-silane	3.88	92	1108	$C_{12}H_{32}O_3Si_3$	308.17
2.	21.26	(2E)-3,7,11,15-tetramethyl-2-hexadecenyl trimethylsilyl ether	15.18	96	2183	$C_{23}H_{48}OSi$	368.35
3.	21.70	2-methyl-7-octadecyne	3.22	82	3462	$C_{19}H_{36}$	264.28
4.	23.30	palmitic acid trimethylsilyl ester	13.07	86	1987	$C_{19}H_{40}O_2Si$	328.28
5.	24.88	linolenic acid trimethylsilyl ester	19.43	81	2208	$C_{21}H_{38}O_2Si$	350.26
6.	27.68	docosoxy(trimethyl)silane	4.94	73	2543	$C_{25}H_{54}OSi$	398.39
7.	29.74	2-trimethylsilyloxytetracosanoic acid methyl ester	11.47	89	2914	$C_{28}H_{58}O_3Si$	470.42
8.	32.77	hexacosoxy(trimethyl)silane	8.40	81	2945	$C_{29}H_{62}OSi$	454.46
9.	39.22	campesterol, trimethylsilyl ether	4.35	88	3249	$C_{31}H_{56}OSi$	472.41
10.	40.40	β -sitosterol trimethylsilyl ether	7.06	85	3344	$C_{32}H_{58}OSi$	486.43
11.	44.01	1-monolinoleoylglycerol trimethylsilyl ether	8.99	99	2742	$C_{27}H_{54}O_4Si_2$	498.36
Total identified			99.99				

The main aliphatic alcohols were docosanol (behenyl alcohol) (5%), hexacosanol (ceryl alcohol) (8%), and glycerol (originally as triacylglycerides, 4%). The identified long-chain aliphatic alcohols are typical for cuticular waxes and membrane-associated lipids (Xiao et al. 2020).

From the group of phytosterols, β -sitosterol and campesterol, with 7% and 4%, respectively, were identified. This class of compounds are essential structural components of plant membranes and, in other species, are implicated in anti-inflammatory and hypocholesterolemic effects (Zhang et al. 2025). The relatively high sterol content in *P. rubra* supports its potential as a source of bioactive sterols, warranting further bioassay-guided studies.

In addition, 2-methyl-7-octadecyne (3%) was found. This less common aliphatic alkyne adds a chemically distinctive component that may be of chemotaxonomic interest.

Taken together, these findings demonstrate that *P. rubra* aerial parts are rich in non-volatile lipids—unsaturated and saturated fatty acids, phytol, long-chain alcohols, and phytosterols—rather than in essential oil constituents. This chemical pattern provides a mechanistic basis for the observed antioxidant and neuroprotective *in vitro* activity. Additionally, comparative work with other *Pulmonaria* species and seasonal or organ-specific analyses would help clarify whether this lipophilic profile is stable and species-specific.

The chemically characterized extract was tested for possible protective activity and enzyme-inhibiting properties in several *in vitro* models.

When administered alone at a concentration of 200 μ g/mL, PR-DCM did not exhibit a statistically significant neurotoxic effect on isolated synaptosomes (Fig. 2). Incubation of synaptosomes with 6-OHDA resulted in a statistically significant decrease in synaptosomal viability by 50%. When applied in combination with the toxic agent, PR-DCM statistically significantly restored synaptosomal viability as follows: 10 mg/mL—by 60%, 50 mg/mL—by 70%, and 100 mg/mL—by 80%.

Administered alone on rat brain synaptosomes, PR-DCM had no toxic effect (at 200 μ g/mL) (Fig. 3). This confirms an absence of direct neurotoxic activity of PR-DCM. The toxic agent 6-OHDA reduced the level of GSH in synaptosomes by 50%. The mutual application of 6-OHDA and PR-DCM on synaptosomes resulted in a statistically significant restoration of the level of GSH as follows: 10 mg/mL—by 60%, 50 mg/mL—by 65%, and 100 mg/mL—by 75%.

The *in vitro* model of 6-OHDA-induced neurotoxicity resembles the neurodegenerative processes occurring in PD. Given that 6-OHDA neurotoxicity is closely linked to dopamine oxidation, reactive oxygen species (ROS), and quinone formation in PD-like degeneration (Stokes et al. 2002), these data suggest that PR-DCM may counteract key oxidative mechanisms relevant to dopaminergic neuron injury. The antioxidant profile of PR-DCM was further supported in mitochondrial and microsomal systems.

On isolated brain mitochondria, PR-DCM alone did not show pro-oxidant activity at 200 μ g/mL, whereas

Figure 2. Effects of PR-DCM, administered alone and in a model of 6-OHDA-induced neurotoxicity, on synaptosomal viability; *** $p < 0.001$ vs. control (non-treated synaptosomes); + $p < 0.05$; ++ $p < 0.01$; +++ $p < 0.001$ vs. 6-OHDA.

Figure 3. Effects of PR-DCM, administered alone and in a model of 6-OHDA-induced neurotoxicity, on GSH level in isolated rat synaptosomes; *** $p < 0.001$ vs. control (non-treated synaptosomes); + $p < 0.05$; ++ $p < 0.01$; +++ $p < 0.001$ vs. 6-OHDA.

t-BuOOH halved mitochondrial GSH levels (Fig. 4) by 50% vs. the control (non-treated mitochondria). In combination with the toxic agent, PR-DCM statistically significantly restored the level of GSH as follows: 10 mg/mL—by 60%, 50 mg/mL—by 70%, and 100 mg/mL—by 80%.

Administered alone, PR-DCM at 200 µg/mL had no significant effect on MDA production in rat brain mitochondria. The oxidative stress-inducing toxic agent applied to the mitochondria resulted in an increase in MDA production by 250% (Fig. 5). In combination with it, the extract resulted in a statistically significant decrease in MDA production as follows: 10 mg/mL—by 65%, 50 mg/mL—by 75%, and 100 mg/mL—by 90%.

On microsomes, administered alone, PR-DCM (at 200 µg/mL) had no pro-oxidant effects (Fig. 6). LPO induced with Fe^{2+} /AA resulted in a 350% increase in MDA produc-

tion vs. the control (non-treated microsomes). In combination with the toxic agent, PR-DCM statistically significantly reduced the formation of MDA as follows: 10 mg/mL—by 70%, 50 mg/mL—by 80%, and 100 mg/mL—by 100%. The latter was the most effective concentration in this experimental model.

These results from varied subcellular *in vitro* models indicate that PR-DCM preserves endogenous antioxidants (GSH) and limits lipid peroxidation under oxidative stress. The extract does not possess pro-oxidative effects. The present findings demonstrate that PR-DCM exerts a pronounced neuroprotective and antioxidant effect in several *in vitro* models of brain oxidative damage, while showing no intrinsic toxicity at the highest tested concentration.

On the activity of the MAOA and MAOB enzymes, PR-DCM at a concentration of 1 µg/mL did not exhibit a sta-

Figure 4. Effects of PR-DCM, administered alone and in a model of *t*-BuOOH-induced neurotoxicity, on GSH level in isolated rat brain mitochondria; *** $p < 0.001$ vs. control (non-treated mitochondria); + $p < 0.05$; ++ $p < 0.01$; +++ $p < 0.001$ vs. *t*-BuOOH.

Figure 5. Effects of PR-DCM, administered alone and in a model of *t*-BuOOH-induced oxidative stress, on MDA production in isolated rat brain mitochondria; *** $p < 0.001$ vs. control (non-treated mitochondria); +++ $p < 0.001$ vs. *t*-BuOOH.

Figure 6. Effects of PR-DCM, administered alone and in a model of non-enzyme-induced lipid peroxidation, on MDA production in rat brain microsomes; *** $p < 0.001$ vs. control (non-treated microsomes); +++ $p < 0.001$ vs. Fe^{2+}/AA .

Figure 7. Effects of PR-DCM (1 µg/mL) on the enzyme activity of *h*MAO-A and *h*MAO-B; *** $p < 0.001$ vs. control (pure *h*MAOB).

Figure 8. Effects of PR-DCM (1 µg/mL) on the enzyme activity of CYP1A2, CYP2D6, and CYP3A4; *** $p < 0.001$ vs. control (non-treated CYP1A2, CYP2D6, and CYP3A4).

tistically significant inhibitory effect compared to the control (pure MAOA/MAOB enzyme) (Fig. 7). The classical inhibitors reduced the activity as follows—chlogyline—of *h*MAOA by 45% and selegiline—of *h*MAOB by 45%.

On the activity of the CYP1A2, CYP2D6, and CYP3A4 enzymes, PR-DCM at a concentration of 1 µg/mL did not exhibit a statistically significant inhibitory effect compared to the control (pure CYP1A2, CYP2D6, and CYP3A4). The classical enzyme inhibitors inhibited the isoforms as follows—α-naphthoflavone of CYP1A2 by 45%, quinidine of CYP2D6—by 45%, and ketoconazole—of CYP3A4 by 45% (Fig. 8).

The results suggest that its protective effects are unlikely to be mediated by MAO inhibition and that the risk of major pharmacokinetic interactions via these CYP isoforms may be low at the tested concentrations.

Taken together, the data support PR-DCM as a promising antioxidant and neuroprotective candidate capable of mitigating PD-like and chemically induced oxidative damage at the synaptosomal, mitochondrial, and microsomal levels, while showing a favorable *in vitro* safety profile. However, the conclusions are limited to acute cell-free and subcellular models; future work should clarify its active constituents, test broader concentration ranges, and

confirm efficacy and safety in neuronal and *in vivo* models of neurodegeneration.

In the present work, the dichloromethane extract of *P. rubra* aerial parts was comprehensively characterized and demonstrated to be dominated by non-volatile lipids, including fatty acids, long-chain aliphatic alcohols, phytol, and phytosterols, with virtually complete coverage of the chromatographic profile by GC–MS after silylation. Functionally, PR-DCM showed a pronounced antioxidant and neuroprotective profile in several subcellular *in vitro* models relevant to Parkinson's disease-like and chemically induced oxidative damage. At concentrations up to 200 µg/mL, the extract did not exert intrinsic toxicity or pro-oxidant effects in isolated rat brain synaptosomes, mitochondria, or microsomes, but significantly preserved GSH levels and reduced MDA formation when co-applied with 6-OHDA, *t*-BuOOH, or Fe²⁺/ascorbic acid, respectively. Moreover, PR-DCM did not significantly inhibit human recombinant MAOA, MAOB, CYP1A2, CYP2D6, or CYP3A4 at the tested concentration, suggesting that its protective effects are unlikely to be mediated via MAO inhibition and that the risk of major pharmacokinetic interactions through these CYP isoforms may be low under the experimental conditions.

Conclusion

These findings identify the lipophilic extract of *P. rubra* as a promising source of bioactive lipid constituents with the capacity to mitigate oxidative stress-related injury at the synaptosomal, mitochondrial, and microsomal levels, while exhibiting a favorable *in vitro* safety and interaction profile. Nevertheless, the present conclusions are confined to acute, cell-free, and subcellular systems, and future work should isolate and quantify the key active components, explore broader dose ranges, and validate efficacy and safety in neuronal and *in vivo* models of neurodegeneration before translational application can be considered.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

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Author contributions

All authors have contributed equally.

Author ORCIDs

Aleksandar Shkondrov <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5091-6058>

Ivan Stambolov <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0198-3438>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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